

Towards an Automated System for Pig Aggression Detection and Tracking

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Abstract

Aggressive behavior in pigs within intensive farming systems poses significant welfare and productivity challenges, yet manual monitoring remains laborious and inconsistent. To address this, we developed an automated deep learning approach combining a VGG16 convolutional backbone with a bidirectional LSTM to detect aggression from video sequences, enhanced by interpretability tools (Grad-CAM, Captum) for model diagnostics. While classification performance was limited (43.9% accuracy, 1.22% aggression recall), mainly related to insufficient variability and quantity of annotated aggressive behaviour episodes at segmentation level, saliency maps confirmed the model's focus on biologically relevant features (e.g., head contacts). We further adapted the dataset for multi-object tracking (MOT) using the MOTChallenge framework, achieving moderate tracking performance (54.4% IDF1, 69.1% MOTA) via CStrack integration. Despite current limitations, this work establishes a critical foundation for precision livestock monitoring by (1) demonstrating the value of explainable AI in behavior analysis and (2) providing a standardized pipeline bridging action recognition with identity-aware tracking—key advancements toward scalable, automated welfare assessment in real-world farming conditions.

Keywords: automated livestock behavior monitoring; VGG16 LSTM animal behavior classification; explainable AI Grad-CAM livestock farming; multi-object tracking (MOT) pigs precision farming; MOTChallenge adaptation animal tracking.

1 Introduction

Understanding and monitoring the behaviour of pigs in livestock environments is essential to ensure animal welfare, prevent injuries, and optimise management practices. Aggressive interactions among pigs, in particular, can lead to stress, wounds, and reduced productivity. However, manually identifying such behaviours from video recordings is time-consuming and prone to inconsistencies.

In this context, the present work proposes an automated pipeline for detecting aggressive behaviours in pigs using deep learning techniques applied to short video sequences. The approach builds upon the work of Chen et al. [1], who demonstrated the effectiveness of combining convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with recurrent layers to classify aggression in pig pens. Our model adopts a similar structure, using a pre-trained VGG16 network to extract frame-level visual features, which are then processed by a bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) layer to capture the temporal dynamics of behaviour.

To enhance the reliability and interpretability of the model, we integrated diagnostic tools such as Grad-CAM and prediction entropy analysis. These tools provide insights into the decision-making process of the neural network and help identify potential learning failures or biases in the data. Despite the implementation of early stopping and data augmentation strategies, our results indicate that the model struggled with generalisation, particularly in recognising aggressive events—highlighting the challenges of learning complex behavioural patterns from limited annotated data.

In a subsequent phase of the project, we explored multi-object tracking (MOT) techniques as a complementary strategy for behaviour analysis. Models such as FairMOT [2] and CStrack [3] combine object detection and re-identification to track individual pigs over time. However, directly applying these models to farm scenarios requires careful adaptation of data and processing pipelines to account for the specific conditions of rural environments, such as occlusions, low contrast, and variable lighting.

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents a literature review, addressing works related to behaviour recognition, multi-object tracking, and model interpretability in computer vision, as well as the evaluation metrics used to assess classification and tracking performance.
- Section 3 details the adopted methodology, including data preparation, model architecture, the training process, and the interpretability techniques applied. It also discusses the results obtained, including classification performance, Grad-CAM visualisations, and tracking performance using MOT-compatible models.
- Section 4 presents the conclusions of the work and proposes future directions for improving models and their applications in production environments.

2 State of the Art

Automated video analysis for monitoring pig behaviour in intensive farming systems has received increasing attention due to its potential to enhance animal welfare monitoring, reduce labour costs, and provide continuous behavioural insights. Computer vision techniques, especially those based on deep learning, allow for the detection of behaviours such as aggression, lethargy, or excessive movement—critical indicators in modern livestock management.

2.1 Classical Approaches

Early works primarily employed handcrafted features and rule-based methods. For instance, Kashiha et al. [4] applied grayscale thresholding combined with blob detection to identify pigs, fitting ellipses to represent their bodies. Tracking relied on manual identity assignment at the start of each video sequence. These detections facilitated the extraction of metrics such as movement trajectories and feeding durations.

In related works, Chen et al. [5, 6] proposed motion-based analysis methods for detecting aggression, extracting features such as optical flow and velocity. These techniques provided the foundation for behaviour quantification, but their generalisation was limited. Our system

extends these approaches by employing learnable temporal models (LSTMs) to better capture dynamic behavioural patterns.

2.2 Deep Learning-Based Behaviour Recognition

To overcome the limitations of classical approaches, recent methods have turned to deep learning for more robust and scalable behaviour recognition. With the widespread adoption of deep learning, architectures based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), particularly LSTMs, became the standard for behaviour recognition. Chen et al. [1] introduced a model that combines VGG16 with LSTM to classify aggressive behaviour in 30-frame video sequences, integrating Grad-CAM to visualise decision-relevant regions.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of using CNN and LSTM to recognise aggressive episodes, adapted from Chen et al. [1].

Figure 1 presents a schematic diagram of the hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture used for recognizing aggressive pig behaviors, adapted from Chen et al. [1]. The model combines a VGG16 convolutional neural network (CNN) for spatial feature extraction from individual video frames with a bidirectional LSTM layer to analyze temporal dynamics across sequences. This architecture addresses both the visual cues (e.g., body posture, head contacts) and motion patterns characteristic of aggression.

Building on this paradigm, we implement a VGG16+LSTM model trained on balanced datasets of aggressive and non-aggressive video clips. To enhance interpretability, we integrated a custom Grad-CAM technique alongside the Captum library, enabling both spatial and temporal visualizations of the model’s attention. This combined approach proved crucial for diagnosing misclassifications and understanding the model’s focus on interaction zones and pig postures during aggression events.

2.2.1 Explainability in Deep Learning: Grad-CAM and Captum

As deep learning models become increasingly complex, understanding their decision-making processes has become crucial, especially in sensitive applications such as animal welfare monitoring. To address this, several explainability techniques have been developed to highlight the regions of an input that contribute most to a model’s prediction.

One of the most prominent methods is **Grad-CAM** (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping), introduced by Selvaraju et al. [7]. Grad-CAM generates coarse localization heatmaps by combining the gradients flowing into the last convolutional layers with their feature maps. This allows for the visualization of class-discriminative regions in an image, helping researchers and practitioners assess whether the model is focusing on semantically relevant areas—such as the heads or interaction zones between pigs when detecting aggression.

Building on this foundation, the **Captum** library was introduced as a unified framework for model interpretability in PyTorch. It includes implementations of various attribution methods such as Saliency Maps, Integrated Gradients, and Layer Grad-CAM. Captum abstracts the complexity of gradient and activation management, enabling more reliable and reproducible explainability workflows across diverse model architectures.

These explainability tools have been increasingly adopted in behaviour recognition pipelines, providing insights not only into model accuracy but also into the reliability and trustworthiness of predictions. In the context of animal behaviour, where wrong decisions may lead to welfare issues or misinterpretation of aggression, such visual diagnostics are essential for model validation and refinement.

2.3 Tracking and Individual Behaviour Monitoring

Accurate tracking of individual animals over time is essential for behaviour modelling and welfare analysis. Classical tracking-by-detection methods often failed under occlusion or lighting variations. To address this, recent approaches such as [3] introduced CSTrack, which combines detection, motion prediction, and re-identification (re-ID) for robust identity preservation.

In our implementation, we adopted the **CSTrack** framework and adapted it for pigs. We integrated detections from **YOLOv8**, a state-of-the-art object detector, and enhanced them with **appearance embeddings** — vector representations of individual visual features extracted from detected objects to help maintain consistent identity assignment across frames. For data annotation, we developed a conversion tool that takes as input **SAM-generated masks** (segmentations produced by the Segment Anything Model) and **COCO-style annotations** (a widely-used format for object detection datasets), outputting identity-preserving tracking files in **LCFormat** — a labeling convention compatible with multi-object tracking benchmarks such as the **MOTChallenge**.

This workflow enabled us to quantify complex behaviours such as repeated chasing, tail-biting, or isolation by associating actions with specific animals over time. Additionally, we extracted spatio-temporal statistics including time spent in different areas, social proximity metrics, and trajectory patterns.

2.3.1 Segmentation-Based Annotation Tools and COCO Format

Recent advances in object detection and tracking have increasingly relied on COCO-style annotations, which offer a standardised and flexible structure for representing segmentation masks, bounding boxes, and class labels. The pycocotools library has become a de facto standard for interacting with such annotations, enabling efficient manipulation of segmentation data and extraction of instance-level information. Originally developed for the MS COCO dataset [8], this toolkit is widely adopted in research and practical applications involving instance segmentation, particularly when converting pixel-wise masks into bounding boxes or preparing annotations for downstream tasks such as multi-object tracking (MOT). Its integration into pipelines facilitates compatibility with benchmark formats like MOTChallenge [9], bridging the gap between raw annotated data and tracking frameworks.

2.3.2 Evaluation Metrics

To comprehensively analyze the tracking accuracy of our model across different scenarios, we utilized the metrics derived from the MOT challenge based on pedestrian datasets [3]. The key metrics include MOTA, IDF1, MOTP, MT, ML, IDS, FP and FN.

Among these, **Multi-Object Tracking Accuracy (MOTA)** is considered the most critical metric in multi-object tracking, as it evaluates the overall accuracy of a multi-object tracking algorithm. The calculation formula for MOTA is:

$$\text{MOTA} = 1 - \frac{FN + FP + IDSW}{GT} \quad (1)$$

where GT represents the number of ground truth objects. The maximum value of MOTA is 1, while its minimum value can reach negative infinity. FN and FP denote the numbers of missed detections and false positives, respectively. $IDSW$ counts the instances of ID switches, indicating how often the tracker incorrectly assigns or changes object IDs. The smaller the $IDSW$, the better the tracker maintains object identity.

IDF1 measures the tracker’s consistency in preserving object identity by combining ID precision and ID recall. The formula for calculating IDF1 is:

$$\text{IDF1} = \frac{2 \cdot IDTP}{2 \cdot IDTP + IDFP + IDFN} \quad (2)$$

where $IDTP$ represents the number of correctly matched objects, $IDFP$ denotes the number of incorrectly matched objects, and $IDFN$ refers to the number of missed objects.

Multiple Object Tracking Precision (MOTP) is a metric used to measure the positional error in tracking. It is defined as:

$$\text{MOTP} = \frac{\sum_{t,i} d_{t,i}}{\sum_t c_t} \quad (3)$$

where c_t represents the number of detection boxes that successfully match with ground truth in frame t , while $d_{t,i}$ measures the distance between matched pairs.

3 Methodology

This section details the methodology developed for detecting and analysing aggressive behaviours in pigs using deep learning techniques. The process encompasses dataset preparation, model development, training procedures, and the application of interpretability methods to evaluate the model.

3.1 Dataset Preparation

The dataset was compiled from video recordings of groups of pigs housed in pens, where episodes of both aggressive and non-aggressive behaviour were manually annotated by experts ¹.

The initial dataset preparation followed an approach inspired by Chen et al., who similarly utilised short video sequences to classify aggressive behaviour in pigs. Each episode consists of a continuous sequence of 30 frames, corresponding to approximately 2 seconds of footage at 15 frames per second. The dataset was organised to ensure that training, validation, and testing sets were mutually exclusive, preventing overlap of episodes derived from the same video source. Classes representing aggressive and non-aggressive behaviours were balanced to avoid bias during training and evaluation. Data augmentation techniques such as horizontal and vertical flipping were applied to enhance model generalisation.

3.2 Model Architecture and Training

The implemented model employs a hybrid architecture combining a deep convolutional neural network for visual feature extraction with a recurrent layer to capture temporal dynamics of the episodes.

Specifically, a pre-trained VGG16 network serves as the feature extractor for individual frames. The extracted features are then fed into a bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) layer, which models temporal dependencies across the sequence.

The LSTM output is passed through fully connected layers to produce a binary classification distinguishing aggressive from non-aggressive behaviour.

Training was conducted using a cross-entropy loss function, optimised with the Adam algorithm with an initial learning rate of $1e-4$. A learning rate scheduler (`ReduceLROnPlateau`) was employed to reduce the learning rate by a factor of 0.1 when the validation loss plateaued, with a patience of 10 epochs to allow recovery. Early stopping was implemented based on validation loss with a patience of 20 epochs to prevent overfitting, stopping training if no improvement was observed within this window. Training were executed using the high-performance server provided by INESC-TEC, equipped with NVIDIA A100 GPUs featuring 40 GB of VRAM.

¹This work utilized expert-annotated videos of pig behavior from the R&D project 'PIGS+CARE' (2017–2019), funded by COMPETE 2020/PORTUGAL 2020 (FEDER) under grant POCI-01-0247-FEDER-017626 (Business R&D Incentive System).

Figure 2: Evolution of total loss and mAP metrics during training.

Figure 2 illustrates the evolution of the total loss and mean average precision (mAP) metrics during the training process of the VGG16+LSTM model. The loss curve shows a steady decline, indicating effective learning, while the mAP curve reflects the model’s improving detection performance over epochs. This visualization confirms that the training process achieved convergence, though the final performance on the test set (as detailed in Section 4.1) highlights limitations in generalization. The alignment of these metrics with early stopping (patience = 20 epochs) underscores the balance between preventing overfitting and maximizing model capability.

3.3 Explainability and Diagnostic Tools

To ensure that the model learns meaningful representations of behaviour, interpretability techniques based on attention mapping were applied, notably Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM), which visualises the regions of the video influencing the model’s decisions. Additionally, gradients across layers were analysed throughout training epochs to detect issues such as vanishing or exploding gradients. Prediction entropy was also computed to assess the stability and confidence of the model’s outputs during training. These interpretability tools enabled the generation of heatmaps over frames, highlighting areas receiving the greatest attention from the network and facilitating qualitative validation of the model’s effectiveness.

These tools allow us to:

- Generate **Grad-CAM heatmaps** for individual frames, showing which regions the model attends to.
- Analyse **layer-wise gradients** to detect vanishing/exploding gradients or dead filters.
- Compute the **entropy of predictions** over time, identifying unstable sequences.
- Save **example visualisations** of both correctly and incorrectly classified sequences.

This interpretability layer was crucial for verifying whether the model focuses on relevant regions (e.g., heads, bites, collisions) when identifying aggression. To generate the Grad-CAM heatmaps, two different implementations were used: a custom method specifically adapted to our model’s architecture, and the Captum library’s abstraction for layer-wise attributions.

The custom Grad-CAM procedure operates by manually identifying the last convolutional layer of the VGG16 backbone and registering its activations and gradients during the forward and backward passes, respectively. The method bypasses the LSTM layers and focuses purely on the convolutional spatial features extracted from each frame. This approach enables us to

generate spatial saliency maps per frame, before temporal integration via the LSTM layer. In parallel, the Captum library was used to verify the results using its LayerGradCam module. This approach automates much of the gradient handling but requires careful specification of the target layer and model handling for temporal sequences. Captum was applied frame-by-frame to isolate the convolutional attention per image prior to LSTM integration. While more abstract and modular, Captum may not capture the temporal dynamics present in the full sequence, which justifies the inclusion of a custom approach for complete interpretability.

3.4 Tracking Data Preparation

To enable multi-object tracking (MOT) evaluation under a standardised benchmark, we converted the annotated data from our pig behaviour videos into the MOTChallenge format, as described in A. Milan et al. [9]. Since the MOTChallenge benchmark and its associated code are primarily designed for human detection, we had to modify the codebase to allow detection and tracking of pigs moving in any direction during testing. This adaptation was essential to accurately represent the pig movements and orientations in our dataset. This format is widely used in the MOT community and allows consistent evaluation across datasets.

The conversion process involved parsing frame-level segmentation annotations (stored in COCO-style JSON files) and extracting bounding boxes via binary masks using the pycocotools library. Using the pycocotools library, we extracted object bounding boxes from binary segmentation masks. Each annotated object was associated with a unique identity (`track_id`) and class label (`category_id`), both preserved in the output. In accordance with the MOTChallenge specifications [9], each sequence was structured as follows:

- A folder named after the session, containing subfolders `img1/`, `gt/`, and `det/`.
- An `img1/` directory containing sequentially named images (e.g., `000001.jpg`).
- A `gt.txt` file with one line per ground truth bounding box in the format:

`<frame>`, `<id>`, `<bb_left>`, `<bb_top>`, `<bb_width>`, `<bb_height>`, 1, 1, 1

- A `det.txt` file following the same structure, but with the ID set to -1 and containing the detection confidence:

`<frame>`, -1, `<x>`, `<y>`, `<w>`, `<h>`, 1

- A `seqinfo.ini` file describing the sequence metadata (e.g., resolution, number of frames).

The dataset was split into training and testing sessions by evenly dividing the available annotated sessions. Two specific sessions, 09:17–09:30 and 09:30–09:42, were manually assigned to the training and test sets, respectively, to ensure that the training and test sets contained videos where episodes of violence occurred. The remaining sessions were divided evenly to maintain a balanced distribution across the sets. To enable seamless integration with CSTrack, we adapted the `CSTrack.yaml` configuration file to reflect the structure and location of our converted dataset. This included specifying the paths to training and testing sequences, adjusting dataset names, and ensuring compatibility with the MOTChallenge directory structure. By aligning the configuration with our data, we ensured that CSTrack correctly loaded the sequences, annotations, and detection hypotheses for training and evaluation. Figure 3 visualizes the discriminative ability of ID embeddings used in the tracking pipeline, which is critical for maintaining consistent identities across frames. The figure includes (a) an example frame with ground truth detections, (b) the corresponding ID embeddings, and (c) a cosine similarity matrix comparing embeddings within the frame. Additionally, (d–f) show template embeddings from previous tracklets and their similarity matrices, with red indicating high correlation. This analysis confirms that the

model learns distinct feature representations for individual pigs, though challenges in occlusion and appearance variation (discussed in Section 4.2) still lead to ID switches. The figure underscores the importance of robust re-identification features for improving tracking continuity in complex farming environments.

This structured approach enabled compatibility with tracking frameworks such as FairMOT and CStrack, facilitating experiments focused on identity preservation and tracking performance.

Figure 3: Visualization about the discriminative ability of ID embeddings: (a) Example Image with ground truth detection results; (b) ID embeddings of the current example frame; (c) Cosine metric matrix between two ID embeddings of the current example frame; (d) Templates (i.e., ID embeddings of the previous tracklets); (e) Cosine metric matrix between two ID embeddings of the template; (f) Cosine metric matrix between ID embeddings of the current example frame and the template. Red color indicates a higher correlation between two features.

Reference Format Specification

The MOTChallenge format requires all input images to be JPEG files named sequentially using six-digit filenames (e.g., 000001.jpg). Ground truth annotations and detection hypotheses are stored as comma-separated value (CSV) files, where each line corresponds to one object instance. As detailed in [9], the ground truth format is as follows:

“The first number indicates the frame number, followed by a unique object ID. The next four numbers represent the top-left bounding box position and its width and height. The seventh value (1 or 0) acts as a flag to indicate whether the instance should be considered for evaluation. The last two values represent object class and visibility ratio.”

This format enables detailed performance evaluation across identity preservation, detection accuracy, and occlusion handling.

4 Results

4.1 Model Performance on the Test Set

The quantitative evaluation results for the proposed VGG16+LSTM model on the test set are presented in Table 1. Despite the training process achieving convergence with early stopping (patience = 20), the model exhibited limited generalisation capability.

The model achieved an overall accuracy of 43.9%, with a notably high false negative rate (48.78%) for the aggression class. This indicates that the model failed to correctly identify the majority of aggressive episodes, misclassifying them as non-aggressive. The low true positive rate (1.22%) further emphasises the model’s difficulty in recognising this behaviour pattern.

Such limitations directly affect the practical applicability of the model, particularly in scenarios where accurate detection of aggressive episodes is crucial for timely preventive or corrective actions. The high false negative rate may result in underreporting these events, reducing the effectiveness of automated behavioural monitoring systems.

Table 1: Model performance on the test set

	Metric	Value
	Accuracy	43.9%

	Predicted Positive	Predicted Negative
Actual Positive	1 (1.22%)	40 (48.78%)
Actual Negative	6 (7.32%)	35 (42.68%)

In practice, the current model performance suggests it is not yet suitable for autonomous use in real environments, as failure to detect aggression could compromise swift interventions and animal welfare. It is recommended to explore strategies to improve model sensitivity, such as architecture adjustments, data balancing techniques, increasing the number of aggressive samples, or incorporating additional data modalities to enrich aggressive behaviour recognition.

4.1.1 Interpretability Analysis with Grad-CAM and Captum

Figure 4: Interpretability methods applied to the aggressiveness classifier. Each image is composed of three parts: the original input frame (left), the standalone heatmap (centre), and the original image overlaid with the corresponding heatmap (right). This layout allows for a direct comparison of the saliency regions highlighted by the Grad-CAM methods.

To better understand the model’s decisions, visual explanation techniques were employed. Grad-CAM was initially used to generate attention maps from the convolutional layers. Although some highlighted regions corresponded to pig interactions, in several cases, irrelevant areas—such as the food zone—were wrongly emphasised, even when no pigs were present.

Figure 4 demonstrates the interpretability methods applied to the aggression classifier, showcasing how Grad-CAM highlights regions of interest in input frames. Each panel displays the original frame (left), the standalone heatmap (center), and an overlay of the heatmap on the original image (right). This visualization reveals whether the model focuses on biologically relevant features (e.g., head contacts during aggression). These insights align with the quantitative results and underscore the value of explainability tools in diagnosing model behavior, even when classification performance is suboptimal.

Captum, a more granular attribution tool, yielded better consistency across a broader set of frames. In particular, it more reliably highlighted regions containing pigs, especially during aggressive events. This indicates that the model, albeit quantitatively weak, had some capacity to focus on semantically meaningful areas.

4.2 Tracking Results and Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of our tracking pipeline, we employed standard metrics from the MOTChallenge benchmark suite, including Multiple Object Tracking Accuracy (MOTA), Multiple Object Tracking Precision (MOTP), ID F1 score (IDF1), number of ID switches (IDSW),

and mostly tracked targets (MT). The evaluation was conducted using the TrackEval toolkit, configured according to the MOT16 settings [9].

The tracking system recorded a total of 1705164 detections across sessions (ranging from 169884 to 274053 per session) and identified 9232 unique IDs, with session-specific counts varying from 504 to 1733.

Table 2 presents an evaluation of CSTrack’s multi-object tracking performance on pig behavior analysis, using manually annotated ground truth data for validation. Focusing on key metrics, the table reveals that while the system achieved a moderate overall MOTA of 50.0%, indicating reasonable detection accuracy, it struggled significantly with identity preservation (IDF1 of just 29.0%) and accumulated 7883 identity switches across sessions. The data shows particular challenges in crowded scenarios, evidenced by high false negatives (507.9K) and false positives (394.3K), suggesting difficulties with occlusions and similar-appearing pigs. Notably, session 09:30 performed best (MOTA 69.1%), while 10:45 showed the weakest results (MOTA 37.9%), highlighting variability under different conditions. These results underscore the need for improved re-identification features and occlusion handling in agricultural computer vision applications.

Table 2: Tracking performance of CSTrack per session using manual annotations.

Session	MOTA	IDF1	Recall	Precision	MT	FP (K)	FN (K)	IDS	FM
09:30	69.1	54.4	86.3	83.6	7	38.4	31.1	538	2364
10:33	38.9	32.6	78.2	66.8	6	88.2	49.6	934	2623
10:45	37.9	19.4	79.5	65.9	6	93.4	46.7	1147	2856
10:58	51.2	20.9	68.4	80.2	5	38.3	71.8	971	2428
11:10	49.3	18.4	65.6	80.5	5	36.1	78.3	1055	2736
11:23	45.2	22.4	60.3	80.8	3	32.7	90.4	1605	3247
11:36	41.8	17.9	59.9	77.4	3	39.9	91.3	1319	3217
11:48	66.4	43.5	78.6	86.7	8	27.4	48.7	314	1237
Overall	50.0	29.0	72.1	76.9	43	394.3	507.9	7883	20708

It is worth emphasising that, despite having only 10 pigs in the experiment, the complexity of their interactions and close proximity complicate continuous and correct identity tracking. The detection component performs reasonably well, as indicated by recall and precision values of 72.1% and 76.9%, respectively, although false positives and false negatives still affect tracking quality. Out of a total of 181872 frames processed, the mostly tracked targets (MT = 43 out of 85 trajectories) show that around half of the objects are well tracked throughout their trajectories, nevertheless, there is room for improvement in recovering partial or lost tracks.

Behavioural Patterns and Tracking Robustness in Multi-Animal Pig Monitoring

The dataset comprises a total of 181872 frames after merging, captured from 10 pigs under observation. Among these, 153920 frames correspond to non-violent behaviours (label = 0), while 27809 frames correspond to violent behaviours (label = 1).

Behavioural distribution across the dataset indicates that the most frequently observed activity is lying (98325 frames), followed by social interaction (46244 frames) and head body knock (21603 frames). Less frequent behaviours include exploration, nosing, and interaction with objects.

Analysis of the average number of interactions per behaviour (Fig. 5) reveals that social interaction (11.41) and head body knock (10.30) are the most interactive behaviours, suggesting they play a significant role in the social dynamics of the pigs. Conversely, behaviours such

as nosing (7.43) and interaction with objects (8.26) show lower interaction averages, possibly indicating more solitary or less frequent activities.

When comparing violent and non-violent behaviours, the average number of interactions per instance is slightly higher in violent behaviours (9.66) than in non-violent ones (9.32), which may reflect the increased activity or complexity associated with aggression.

Figure 5: Average number of ids by behaviour type.

It is important to note that, although there are only 10 pigs in the dataset, the tracking system occasionally detects more or fewer targets than this number. Overestimations occur mainly due to false positives, such as the food area being mistakenly detected as a pig, likely caused by similar textures or shapes in the scene. Conversely, underestimations arise when pigs are partially or fully occluded by other animals, or when the detection fails due to motion blur or poor lighting conditions. These challenges contribute to identity switches and track fragmentation, underscoring the necessity for enhanced detection accuracy and more robust re-identification features to maintain consistent tracking identities.

These findings highlight the complex social behaviour of a relatively small group of pigs and the challenges posed to automated tracking systems. Improving both detection accuracy and identity association will be essential to enhance tracking continuity and reduce identity switches, thus enabling more precise behavioural quantification in future research. Overall, these results highlight the importance of enhancing both the detection robustness and the data association steps in the tracking pipeline to improve identity continuity and reduce fragmentation. Future work could focus on integrating better re-identification features and temporal consistency models.

5 Discussion

Despite the methodological rigor and comprehensive evaluation, the model’s performance on the test set revealed significant limitations. The final accuracy was 43.9%, with a particularly low true positive rate (1.22%) for detecting aggression. Most aggressive episodes were misclassified as non-aggressive, resulting in a high false negative rate (48.78%).

These results suggest that, while the model learned to distinguish some features relevant to aggression, it failed to generalise effectively. Possible contributing factors include:

- **Insufficient variability and quantity** of annotated aggressive behaviour episodes, as

the dataset mainly contains interactions from the same pigs within the same pen, limiting the model’s exposure to diverse aggression patterns.

- **Imbalance in intra-class complexity**, where non-aggressive behaviour was more homogeneous and thus easier to model, whereas aggression exhibited greater variation and subtlety.
- **Loss of temporal resolution**, as episodes were limited to short sequences (2 seconds), potentially missing longer-term behavioural cues needed for robust classification.
- **Underutilisation of motion cues**, with no optical flow or motion-specific features included in the model, reducing its ability to detect dynamic actions characteristic of aggression.

Our **PigsMot** dataset, which consists of carefully annotated pig movement sequences in a real farm environment, poses unique challenges such as occlusions, varying illumination, and complex interactions among animals. This dataset serves as a critical testbed to evaluate the adaptability of each tracking algorithm in practical, non-ideal conditions.

Results highlight the strengths and limitations of each approach, revealing that while some methods excel in controlled or synthetic environments, their performance may degrade in real-world scenarios like those captured in **PigsMot**. This comparison underscores the necessity for robust tracking solutions tailored to agricultural applications and animal behavior monitoring.

Table 3 presents a comparative evaluation of multiple state-of-the-art multi-object tracking (MOT) methods across various scenes, including our manually annotated dataset, **PigsMot**. The aim is to assess how well each tracker performs under distinct environmental conditions and levels of complexity.

The evaluated methods include classical and deep learning-based trackers widely adopted in animal monitoring and MOT benchmarks, as described by Liu et al. [10]. Metrics such as *MOTA* (Multiple Object Tracking Accuracy), *IDF1* (ID F1 Score), *FP* (False Positives), *FN* (False Negatives), and *IDs* (ID switches) are reported to provide a comprehensive overview of tracking quality.

Table 3: Comparison of tracking methods in different scenes.

Method	Scenario	MOTA↑	IDF1↑	MT↑	ML↓	FP↓	FN↓	IDS↓
Liu et al.- Deep-OC-SORT (YOLOv8)	night-in	64.1	71.9	5	3	0	6436	25
	night-out	28.2	38.5	1	9	0	22759	298
	daytime-out	90.0	78.2	13	0	575	527	244
Liu et al.- FairMOT	night-in	68.8	56.8	6	1	760	4780	85
	night-out	33.5	45.5	7	4	6266	14972	92
	daytime-out	90.5	70.7	12	0	535	585	161
Liu et al.- CStrack	night-in	64.7	48.8	5	3	1	6191	79
	night-out	52.8	44.4	10	4	1142	13849	174
	daytime-out	91.1	69.4	11	0	333	679	194
Liu et al.- SDGTrack	night-in	78.1	81.9	9	0	1558	3371	11
	night-out	69.6	82.6	17	2	1678	9342	10
	daytime-out	95.0	90.8	12	0	176	500	3
Ours - CStrack (PigsMot)	daytime-out	50.0	29.0	43	6	394300	507880	7883

Across public benchmark scenarios, particularly in controlled “daytime-out” settings, most methods (e.g., FairMOT, CStrack, Deep-OC-SORT) demonstrate high MOTA scores above 90%. However, performance degrades notably in low-light or occlusion-heavy scenes, such as “night-out”, where MOTA drops to as low as 28.2% (Deep-OC-SORT) or 33.5% (FairMOT).

In contrast, SDGTrack consistently outperforms others in all conditions, especially under day scenes, achieving both high MOTA (78.1–95.0)% and IDF1 (81.9–90.8)%, with very low ID switch rates.

When applying CStrack to our PigsMot dataset, the performance drops substantially, with a MOTA of 50.0% and an IDF1 of only 29.0%. The tracker registered a very high number of false positives (394300) and ID switches (7883), which underscores the unique challenges of the dataset and suggests that existing tracking models, while effective in public benchmarks, struggle to generalize to high-density, unstructured animal behaviour scenes. This highlights the need for more specialized detection-reID integration and better temporal consistency models tailored for livestock behaviour analysis.

6 Conclusion

This work explored the use of deep learning techniques to automatically detect and interpret aggressive behaviour in pigs, with the overarching aim of improving animal welfare monitoring in intensive farming environments. The study covered the end-to-end pipeline from data collection and labelling to model design, training, evaluation, and interpretability. The main contributions of this work are:

- A behaviourally annotated dataset of pig interactions was curated, containing balanced episodes of aggressive and non-aggressive actions in video form. These episodes were standardised to 30-frame sequences at 15 FPS to capture short-term behaviour dynamics.
- A deep learning model architecture was implemented, combining a pre-trained convolutional neural network (VGG16) for spatial feature extraction with a bidirectional LSTM layer for temporal modelling. This hybrid structure was tailored to capture both the appearance and evolution of behaviours across time.
- A suite of interpretability and diagnostic tools was integrated into the training and evaluation pipeline. These included Grad-CAM (custom and Captum-based), gradient flow analysis, prediction entropy tracking, and visual inspection of both successful and failed predictions. This facilitated qualitative validation of the model’s decision-making process.
- A methodology was developed to convert annotated behavioural sequences into the MOTChallenge format, enabling the application of multi-object tracking frameworks for future spatiotemporal analysis and integration with tracking-based approaches such as CStrack.

The interpretability component of this work proved essential for understanding the model’s behaviour. Grad-CAM maps showed that, in several cases, the model focused attention on semantically relevant regions such as pigs’ heads and contact zones during aggressive events. However, there were also instances where attention was misdirected to irrelevant areas, such as empty feeding stations or walls, indicating incomplete learning.

Captum’s more granular attribution approach produced more stable and focused visualisations, suggesting its value as a debugging and validation tool. Nonetheless, even with these insights, interpretability alone could not compensate for the lack of model generalisation, though it did offer valuable diagnostic information.

Given the limitations observed, several avenues for future research are proposed:

- **Data Augmentation and Expansion:** Increasing the number and diversity of aggressive behaviour samples, potentially through synthetic data generation or active learning techniques, could improve the model’s generalisability.
- **Multimodal Integration:** Including additional data streams such as multiple cameras, depth maps, optical flow, or audio could enrich the feature space and provide stronger cues for aggression detection.

- **Model Architecture Refinement:** Exploring attention-based transformers, 3D CNNs, or temporal convolution networks (TCNs) may yield better representations of complex behaviour over time.
- **End-to-End Spatiotemporal Detection:** Integrating the classification model with a robust multi-object tracking pipeline would enable continuous, real-time aggression monitoring with spatial context.
- **Explainability-Driven Training:** Incorporating attention supervision or interpretability constraints during training might guide the model to focus on behaviourally relevant regions more consistently.
- **Spatiotemporal Integration with Tracking Pipelines:** Building upon the MOT Challenge annotation pipeline developed in this work, future research can incorporate CSTrack or similar object tracking methods to maintain individual pig identities across frames, such as the method SDGTrack used in [10]. This would allow for continuous behaviour monitoring, event localisation, and improved robustness in aggression detection by leveraging motion continuity and identity-preserving temporal context.

This work provided a solid foundation for the automatic detection of aggression in pigs using deep learning, combining both classification and interpretability in a single pipeline. While the results did not reach deployment-ready performance, the tools, analysis, and insights presented here serve as a valuable basis for future improvements.

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